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Exploring the Key Factors Affecting Labor Force Participation in Pakistan: The Role of Internet, Foreign Direct Investment, and Trade Channels

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the factors influencing individuals' decisions to join the workforce in Pakistan. The primary aim is to understand how variables such as Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), internet access, capital, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and trade impact labor force participation using time series data from 1998 to 2022. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) regression model was employed to estimate the relationships. The results indicate that FDI, internet access, capital, and GDP positively affect labor force participation. However, the impact of trade on labor force participation is influenced by factors such as the type of trade, industry, and government policies. By exploring these key factors, the study provides insights into the potential mechanisms through which internet connectivity, FDI, and trade channels affect labor force participation. These findings can help policymakers understand labor market dynamics in Pakistan and develop strategies to enhance labor force participation.

Keywords: Labor force participation; Internet penetration; Foreign direct investment; Trade; ARDL technique; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

The labor force includes individuals available for work who are aged 16 and above. Developing countries often face low levels of labor force participation (Shahid, 2014). Provision of skilled labor can improve productivity, and the export of final products can drive economic growth (Ali et al., 2015). To foster economic growth, governments should prioritize investments in human capital and physical infrastructure. This can be achieved through policies that promote education, healthcare, and workforce development, as well as investments in fixed assets such as roads, bridges, and technology. These efforts create job opportunities, stimulate economic activity, and drive sustainable growth (Khan et al., 2023). Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is a key driver of international capital flows, enabling the transfer of capital, technology, and expertise from developed to developing countries. It is a critical component of global economic development and cooperation. Many countries, especially developing nations, aim to attract FDI, anticipating long-term economic growth from additional stable resources. Labor force, trade openness, and economic freedom are other key determinants of FDI, which in turn stimulate income growth (Sasarara, 2016).

In Pakistan, GDP per capita is positively and significantly influenced by trade openness, labor force participation rate, FDI, and the exchange rate. However, a negative and statistically significant effect is found for the interaction term of trade openness multiplied by the exchange rate (Bhatti et al., 2023). The Internet contributes to global social, political, and sustainable economic growth. Particularly, technology, FDI, and trade in green economic growth are imperative factors contributing to a country's development (Iqbal K. et al., 2023). To enhance its infrastructure, the government of Pakistan can adopt effective policies to leverage foreign investment. FDI, remittances, and official development assistance (ODA) can be key drivers of economic growth. For countries like Pakistan with limited financial resources, FDI is a crucial source of funding. Additionally, science and technology play a vital role in developing innovative techniques that drive economic progress and sustainable development (Rehman et al., 2023). Increasing foreign direct investment, gross capital formation, and industrialization enhances employment opportunities in Pakistan in both the long and short term. In contrast, gross domestic income, economic growth, and population growth negatively affect employment opportunities in both the long and short term (Khan et al., 2023). Human capital and trade liberalization play a central role in economic growth (Luqman et al., 2023). In the developing world, digital literacy is a significant barrier to adopting and utilizing the Internet and digital technologies. However, by empowering individuals to efficiently access and utilize valuable online information, digital literacy can unlock economic opportunities, contributing to human development and poverty reduction. Bridging the digital divide helps individuals acquire new skills, access knowledge, and connect with global markets, fostering sustainable economic growth and social progress (Ali et al., 2023). Technology has rapidly developed to meet the needs of information sharing. Communication technology aims to collaborate, enhance communication, and connect communities globally. The Internet, a network that connects users worldwide rapidly, was introduced and developed by J.C.R. Licklider in 1962. The Internet helps people connect globally and locally, sharing ideas, knowledge, and communication through exchanging packets (Mukhtar et al., 2023).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review is divided into three subsections. The first section reviews the literature on Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), and their impact on the labor force. The second section focuses on Trade and Gross Capital Formation with the impact of the labor force. The third section examines the literature on the Internet and its impact on the labor force. Iqbal et al. (2014) investigated the relationship between FDI, GDP, and their combined impact on labor force participation in Pakistan. Developed countries have increasingly recognized the significance of FDI as a catalyst for economic growth, particularly in developing nations. FDI is especially crucial for closed economies. This study analyzed data from Pakistan between 1983 and 2012 and found that FDI positively and significantly impacts GDP, and both variables positively influence labor force participation in Pakistan. The study highlights the benefits of FDI, including technology transfer, skilled labor, and skill transfer to host nations, suggesting that attracting FDI is essential for promoting economic growth and development in Pakistan. Shahid (2014) examined the short and long-run relationships between economic growth, labor force participation, and gross capital formation using data from 1980 to 2012 collected from the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics and the State Bank of Pakistan. The study shows a long-run relationship between the variables, with a short-term negative significant association between labor force participation, gross capital, and economic growth. Overall, the relationship between these variables is positively significant. Jehangir et al. (2020) investigated the effect of FDI and GDP on economic growth and labor force participation in Pakistan, examining both long-run and short-run relationships from 1974 to 2018. The study found that in the long run, gross fixed capital and labor force participation positively impact economic growth. As FDI increases, GDP gradually increases through investment, raising the employment rate in Pakistan and boosting the economy. Mazher et al. (2020) aimed to measure the impact of FDI on unemployment in Pakistan using time series data from 1972 to 2014. The results revealed that in the long run, FDI plays an important role in reducing unemployment in Pakistan, although its short-run impact is significant. The government should take measures to increase foreign capital in the form of FDI to reduce unemployment rates in Pakistan.

Khan et al. (2023) examined the impact of FDI on employment opportunities in Pakistan, focusing on the Gwadar Seaport, and analyzed relationships between gross capital formation, gross domestic income, economic growth, population growth, and employment opportunities using data from 1990 to 2019. The study revealed significant long-term and short-term relationships between the variables, showing that increased FDI and GDP led to a higher labor force participation rate in Pakistan. The study highlights the potential of FDI and the Gwadar Seaport to stimulate employment opportunities and suggests that investing in infrastructure projects can create jobs and stimulate economic development. Malik (2015) analyzed the impact of FDI and GDP on Pakistan's economy, particularly focusing on the labor force using data from 2008 to 2013. The study found that these variables positively impact the economy and labor force participation in Pakistan. The government should take solid steps to increase FDI and domestic investment, stabilize the exchange rate, and attract more investors to benefit the country's economic condition. Higher FDI attracts more educated labor, increasing the labor force participation rate in the economy. Amir et al. (2015) examined the education levels of the labor force in Pakistan as a measure of human capital using time series data from 1973 to 2013. The study found that education significantly impacts economic growth in both the long run and short run, highlighting the importance of investing in the labor force's education for sustainable economic development. Investing in gross capital formation leads to a better-educated and skilled labor force, enhancing Pakistan's economic growth. Bhatti (2023) studied how trade affects a country's economy using data from 1972 to 2021. GDP per capita in Pakistan was positively and significantly influenced by trade openness, the labor force participation rate, FDI, and the exchange rate. Fatima et al. (2020) explored the empirical impact of trade openness on GDP growth, considering the role of human capital accumulation in economic trade integration. The results suggest that the relationship between trade openness and GDP growth is indirect and depends on the level of human capital accumulation. When countries have low levels of human capital accumulation, trade may negatively impact GDP growth. This research examines this relationship in both developed and developing

countries over a 34-year period (1980-2014). S. Zahir et al. (2020) investigated the causal links between GDP, Gross Fixed-Capital Formation (GFCF), and Trade Deficits in Pakistan using time-series data from 1986 to 2013. The study found that trade deficits negatively impact GDP, suggesting that trade deficits can hinder economic growth. The accumulation of capital (GFCF) is essential for increasing a country's tangible equity by investing in economic and social infrastructures. The study highlights the importance of understanding the causal relationships between GDP, GFCF, and trade deficits in Pakistan.

Ahmad et al. (2024) aimed to investigate the factors influencing Pakistan's economic growth from 1972 to 2021, examining the causal link between economic variables and growth. The study showed that human and physical capital have a statistically significant beneficial impact on economic growth, suggesting that bank lending, exports, imports, and the labor force in employment did not impact economic growth. Kazmi et al. (2020) highlighted the critical role of technological advancement in developing industries and economies, directly impacting worker operations and performance. Technological modernization eliminates some jobs but creates new opportunities and labor markets. The study suggests that developing countries, such as Pakistan, should proactively address the impacts of Industry 4.0 by upskilling workers and creating jobs in new technologies to drive economic growth and build a future-ready workforce. Yasmeen et al. (2015) investigated the effect of internet usage on the economic growth of South Asian countries, particularly Pakistan, using annual time-series data from 1995 to 2013. The study found that capital and labor positively impact Pakistan's economic growth in the long run. Internet usage also has a positive long-term impact on economic growth, indicating that increased internet penetration can contribute to economic development. The findings suggest that investing in internet infrastructure and promoting digital literacy can drive economic growth and development. Hasan et al. (2021) examine the feasibility of working and studying from home in Pakistan. They utilize the recently released 2018–19 Pakistan Social and Living Standards Measurement (PSLM) Survey, which provides valuable insights into the country's employment outcomes, education, and digital access. Their analysis reveals significant challenges in homeschooling due to limited television and internet access, disproportionately affecting girls. However, the government's initiative to launch the Tele School TV channel offers a promising solution to bridge this gender gap in education and promote inclusive learning. Khan et al. (2022) study the rapid escalation of Mobile Phone and Internet Technology Usage (MPITU) in organizational systems to evaluate its effectiveness in enhancing sales productivity and marketing channels among wheat growers. They examine its impact on their incomes using a dataset of 580 wheat growers from four districts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province (KPK), Pakistan. The study finds that MPITU has significantly improved agricultural structures and revolutionized agricultural activities, enhancing smart agriculture. MPITU positively impacts wheat growers' productivity and marketing channels, leading to increased incomes. Amber et al. (2023) investigate the gender and rural-urban digital divide in Pakistan and examine the impact of mobile phone ownership on women's labor force participation and economic well-being. The study uses the Pakistan Social and Living Standards Measurement Survey (2019-2020) to analyze the gender and rural-urban digital divide and employs an instrumental variable approach to assess the effect of mobile phone ownership on women's labor force participation. The findings indicate that women in Pakistan face significant barriers in accessing mobile phones and smartphones due to socio-cultural norms and other factors, perpetuating the gender digital divide. Mobile phone ownership positively impacts women's labor force participation, enabling them to make informed decisions about their work and economic lives. Upskilling women in digital tools and providing them with mobile phones can have wider implications for their economic well-being and empowerment. This study highlights the importance of addressing the gender digital divide in Pakistan and promoting mobile phone ownership among women to enhance their economic empowerment and labor force participation. Policymakers and stakeholders can use these findings to develop targeted interventions and programs to bridge the digital divide and promote gender equality.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Table 1 shows the list of variables for ready reference.

Table 1: List of Variables

Variables	Symbol	Unit	A prior Effect
Labor Force Participation Rate	Labor	%	Positive
Internet Use	Internet	% of population	Positive
Foreign Direct Investment Inflows	FDI	Current US\$	Positive
Gross Domestic Product	EC	Annual %	Positive
Gross Capital Formation	Capital	Annual %	Positive
Trade	Trade	% of GDP	Positive

Source: World Bank (2023).

A unit root test is a statistical measure used to determine if a time series is stationary or non-stationary, helping researchers identify if a dataset has a long-term trend or is simply random fluctuations. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is a commonly used unit root test that compares the data to a null hypothesis of non-stationarity, rejecting the null hypothesis if the test statistic exceeds the critical value, indicating that the data is stationary. A stationary time series has consistent properties over time, making it reliable and predictable, remaining constant without significant trends or patterns, and is essential in statistics and time series analysis for modeling and forecasting. In contrast, non-stationary data has means, variances, and covariances that change over time, exhibiting trends, cycles, random walks, or combinations of these, making it unpredictable and unable to be modeled or forecasted. The ADF test is a statistical tool used to detect unit roots in time series data, and is an augmented version of the Dickey-Fuller test, suitable for larger

and more complex time series models, with the ADF statistic being a negative number used to determine the presence of a unit root.

The AR(1) model is a simple autoregressive model that describes a time series as a function of its previous value, plus an error term. The model is:

$$X_t = \varphi X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

where X_t is the value of the series at time t , φ is a parameter that measures the degree of persistence, and ε_t is a white noise error term.

The three cases mentioned refer to the behavior of the series based on the value of φ :

Case 1:

$|\varphi| < 1$ (stationary)

- The series is stationary, meaning it has constant mean and variance over time.
- The series exhibits a stable pattern, with fluctuations around a constant mean.
- Example: $\varphi = 0.67$ (Figure 16.1)

Case 2:

$|\varphi| > 1$ (explosive)

- The series is not stationary, and its behavior is explosive.
- The series exhibits rapid growth or decline, with no stable pattern.
- Example: $\varphi = 1.26$ (Figure 16.2)

Case 3:

$\varphi = 1$ (unit root, non-stationary)

- The series has a unit root, meaning it is not stationary and has a persistent pattern.
- The series exhibits a random walk behavior, with no tendency to revert to a mean.

Cointegration is a statistical technique used to identify long-term correlations between time series processes. Introduced by Nobel laureates Robert Engle and Clive Granger in 1987, cointegration tests determine whether two or more non-stationary time series are integrated in a way that prevents them from deviating from equilibrium in the long term. In other words, cointegration tests reveal whether two variables are tied to the same average price over a specific period, and to what extent they are sensitive to each other. By applying cointegration tests, researchers can uncover hidden relationships between seemingly unrelated time series, providing valuable insights for forecasting, modeling, and decision-making in fields like economics, finance, and more.

$$\theta_1 Y_t + \theta_2 X_t = \mu_t - I(0)$$

An Error Correction Model (ECM) is a powerful tool for analyzing multiple time series data that exhibit cointegration, meaning they share a common long-term stochastic trend. ECMs are particularly useful for estimating both short-term and long-term relationships between time series variables. The "error-correction" aspect of ECMs refers to the idea that any deviation from long-run equilibrium in the previous period influences short-term dynamics. In essence, ECMs quantify how quickly a dependent variable returns to equilibrium after changes in other variables, providing valuable insights into the underlying relationships between time series data. By directly estimating the speed of adjustment, ECMs offer a theoretically-driven approach to understanding complex dynamics in time series data.

$$\Delta Y_t = a_0 + \beta_1 \Delta X_1 - \pi_1 \mu_t - 1 + Y_t$$

The Engle-Granger Two-Step method is a widely used approach for testing cointegration in time series data. The process begins by generating residuals from a static regression, which are then examined for unit roots using tests such as the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. If the residuals are found to be stationary, it indicates cointegration between the time series. In contrast, the Johansen test offers a more comprehensive approach, enabling the detection of multiple cointegrating relationships between multiple non-stationary time series. While the Johansen test provides greater flexibility, it relies on asymptotic properties, making it more suitable for large sample sizes. Using the Johansen test to identify cointegration among multiple time series helps avoid the issues that arise when errors are carried forward to subsequent steps. Johansen's test comes in two main forms, i.e., Trace tests and Maximum Eigenvalue test. Trace tests evaluate the number of linear combinations in a time series data, i.e., K to be equal to the value K_0 , and the hypothesis for the value K to be greater than K_0 . It is illustrated as follows:

$$H_0: K = K_0$$

$$H_0: K > K_0$$

When applying the trace test to determine cointegration in a sample, setting K_0 to zero allows us to test the null hypothesis. If the null hypothesis is rejected, it indicates the presence of a cointegration relationship in the sample. Therefore, rejecting the null hypothesis confirms the existence of cointegration. An Eigenvalue is a non-zero vector that, when subjected to a linear transformation, is scaled by a scalar factor. The Maximum Eigenvalue test is similar to the Johansen trace test, but with a key difference in the null hypothesis. While the trace test examines the null hypothesis of no cointegration, the Maximum Eigenvalue test examines the null hypothesis of at most r cointegrating relationships, where r is the number of cointegrating vectors.

$$H_0: K = K_0$$

$$H_0: K = K_0 + 1$$

If $K=K_0$ and the null hypothesis is rejected, it indicates that there is only one possible way to combine the variables to achieve a stationary process. This suggests that the variables are cointegrated, and there is only one cointegrating equation. On the other hand, if $K_0=m-1$ and the null hypothesis is rejected, it implies that there are M possible linear combinations of the variables that can produce a stationary process. However, this is only possible if the individual variables in the time series are already stationary. In other words, there is no cointegration, and the variables are already stationary on their own.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is a powerful econometric tool for examining both long-term and short-term relationships between multiple time series variables. This model consists of two key components: 1. Autoregressive (AR) component: This part of the model incorporates lagged values of the dependent variable, capturing short-term dynamics and the ways in which the variable responds to its own past values. 2. Distributed Lag (DL) component: This component includes lagged values of the explanatory variables, revealing how these variables influence the dependent variable over time. The DL component accounts for the delayed effects of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable. By combining these two components, the ARDL model provides a comprehensive understanding of the complex relationships between time series variables, enabling researchers to disentangle both short-term and long-term effects.

$$1: y_t = \alpha_0 + a_1 y_{t-1} + \alpha_2 X_t + x_3 X_{t-1} + \xi - 1$$

2: Σ merge equation of both AR and DL approach.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model has two fundamental assumptions: Data should have stationary either on I (0) or I (1) or on both. In addition to this, if any of the variables in the data has stationary at I (2), ARDL Model cannot run.

1: I (0) & I (1)

2: I (0) & I (0)

3: I (1) & I (1)> apply Johnson’s cointegration test

4: Shows best results on Small Sample size (finite data)

5: show short run- long run results.

6: use simultaneously ECM in the equation.

β_0 is called the short-run or impact multiplier it describes how a one-unit size one-moment (i.e. temporary) increase of T_x affects T_y . However, it is common to focus on the long-run, or total, multiplier. The delay (interim) multiplier can be interpreted as the effect on the dependent variable in period $t+s$, resulting from an instant (sustained) shock to an independent variable in period t .

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 and 3 presents descriptive statistics and correlation matrix of the variables for ready reference.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	LABOR	INTERNET	FDI	GDP	CAPITAL	TRADE
Mean	59403225	8.922961	-1.81E+09	4.113091	3.151144	28.86270
Median	60255359	8.000000	-1.76E+09	4.217942	3.606978	29.46983
Maximum	78863081	21.03721	-2.58E+08	7.831256	17.84331	34.34896
Minimum	40910245	0.043948	-5.49E+09	-1.274087	-9.696390	21.45997
Std. Dev.	10920387	6.111568	1.41E+09	1.980865	6.992034	3.780060
Skewness	0.003842	0.463946	-1.299036	-0.356729	-0.251076	-0.254722
Kurtosis	1.882652	2.454278	4.222249	3.509444	2.470960	1.802138

Source: Author’s estimation.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Probability	LABOR	INTERNET	FDI	EC	CAPITAL	TRADE
LABOR	1 ----					
INTERNET	0.964 (0.00)	1 ----				
FDI	-0.142 (0.157)	-0.16 (0.10)	1 ----			
EC	-0.04 (0.65)	0.009 (0.92)	0.003 (0.97)	1 ----		
CAPITAL	-0.02 (0.77)	-0.00 (0.969)	-0.15 (0.1360)	0.70 (0.00)	1 ----	
TRADE	0.05 (0.57)	0.028 (0.77)	-0.32 (0.0008)	-0.22 (0.024)	-0.23 (0.019)	1 ----

Source: Author’s estimation. Small bracket shows probability value.

Table 4 shows the ADF unit root estimates and found that labor, EC, and Capital are level stationary variables while the remaining variables are first differenced stationary.

Table 4: ADF Unit Root Test Estimates

Value	Level		First difference	
	intercepts	Trend/intercept	intercepts	Trend/intercepts
Labor	0.4481 (0.9809)	-3.5518 (0.0594)	-0.4022 (0.005)	-3.9882 (0.0242)
Internet	1.4258 (0.9985)	-2.3518 (0.3924)	-2.5575 (0.1159)	-2.299 (0.4175)
FDI	-2.4805 (0.1329)	-2.2314 (0.4515)	-3.0490 (0.0451)	-3.1333 (0.1224)
EC	-3.6212 (0.0130)	-3.5756 (0.0537)	-6.2532 (0.000)	-6.1015 (0.0003)
Capital	-4.0947 (0.0051)	-3.9590 (0.0274)	-6.5252 (0.0000)	-6.3965 (0.0001)
Trade	-2.3345 (0.1700)	-2.3125 (0.4120)	-4.1464 (0.0041)	-4.1902 (0.0160)

Source: Author's estimation. Small bracket shows probability value.

The unit root test is used to determine if a time series is stationary or non-stationary. The test statistics and p-values suggest that labor, FDI, and trade have unit roots in the level form, which means they are non-stationary in their raw form. However, when they are differenced (i.e., their first differences are taken), they become stationary. Internet penetration has a unit root in both the level and first difference forms, which suggests that it is non-stationary and may require further transformation or differencing to achieve stationarity. Economic cooperation and capital are stationary in both the level and first difference forms, which suggests that they are already stationary and do not require differencing. The presence of unit roots in some of the time series may indicate the presence of stochastic trends, which can have important implications for forecasting and modeling. The results of the unit root test can also inform the choice of model specification and the use of differencing or detrending techniques to achieve stationarity. It's important to note that the unit root test is just one tool for evaluating stationarity, and it's not always conclusive. Other tests and visual inspections of the data (e.g., plotting the time series and its autocorrelation function) can provide additional insights into the stationarity of the data. Table 5 shows the pantula estimates for ready reference.

Table 5: Pantula Test Estimates

Data Trend	None	None	Linear	Linear	Quadratic
	No Intercept	Intercept	Intercept	Intercept	Intercept
Test Type	No Trend	No Trend	No Trend	Trend	Trend
Trace	2	3	1	2	5
Max-Eig	1	1	1	2	2

Source: Author's estimation.

The Pantula test is an extension of Augmented Dickey- Fuller test and is used to determine the presence of unit roots in time series data. Based on the table I can interpret that there are two cointegration relationships between the variables, meaning they share a long-term common stochastic trend. The Trace and Max-Eig columns report the test statistics for the cointegration test. The numbers in the 1, 2, 3, and 5 columns likely refer to the cointegration equations being tested. Table 6 shows the Johnsons cointegration estimates.

Table 6: Johnsons Cointegration Test Estimates

Hypothesized	Eigenvalue	Trace	0.05	Prob.**
No. of CE(s)		Statistic	Critical Value	
None *	0.962714	188.4758	103.8473	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.872742	112.8257	76.97277	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.638369	65.41029	54.07904	0.0035
At most 3 *	0.612950	42.01629	35.19275	0.0079
At most 4	0.508772	20.18463	20.26184	0.0512
At most 5	0.153585	3.835156	9.164546	0.4372

Source: Author's estimation.

Johnson's cointegration test is used to determine the number of cointegration relationships between multiple time series. The test suggests that there are at least three cointegration relationships among the time series. Cointegration can imply a long-term equilibrium relationship between time series, which can be modeled using different techniques. The test is examining the null hypothesis of no cointegration (None) against the alternative hypothesis of at most 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 cointegrating relationships. The Eigenvalue column reports the eigenvalues of the variance matrix, which are used to calculate the test statistics. The Statistic column reports the test statistics, which are compared to the Critical Value column to determine the significance of the test. The Prob column reports the p-values associated with each test statistic. Table 7 shows the ARDL short-run estimates.

Table 7: ARDL Short-Run Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LABOR (-2)	0.707	0.201	3.513	0.012
INTERNET (-1)	739114.1	355482.1	2.079	0.082
FDI (-1)	0.0005	0.0002	2.102	0.080
EC	-353802.0	115157.4	-3.072	0.021
CAPITAL	59597.91	29835.77	1.997	0.092
TRADE (-2)	122410.4	62168.38	1.969	0.096
C	15506030	3362467.	4.611	0.003

Source: Author's estimation.

The coefficient table shows the estimated coefficient, standard errors, t-statistics and p-value of each variable. Labor has a significant positive coefficient indicating a strong lagged effect, Internet, FDI, EC, Trade and capital has significant positive coefficient indicating a significant impact on dependent variable. The significant of labor and capital suggest that investing in human capital and physical infrastructure is crucial for economic growth. The positive impact of internet implies that increasing access to digital technology and online services can improve economy. The results are linked with the previous study, The ARDL approach revealed that internet usage has a positive long-term impact on economic growth, indicating that increasing internet penetration can contribute to sustained economic expansion. However, to fully harness the potential of internet usage and unlock its significant impact on economic growth, efforts are needed to enhance its effective utilization, such as improving digital literacy, expanding access to high-speed internet, and promoting e-commerce and digital entrepreneurship (Yasmeen et al 2015). The marginal significance of foreign direct investment suggests that attracting foreign investment contribute to economic growth but the relationship maybe complex and dependent on other factors. Previous study concluded that The ARDL co-integration results reveal a significant long-run relationship between the variables, with a favorable R-square value indicating a well-fitting model. In the short run, physical capital, foreign direct investment, human capital, trade, and labor are all significant factors, with labor and trade having a negative impact and the others having a positive impact. The error correction term is negative and significant, indicating a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. In the long run, physical capital, FDI, human capital, and trade have a positive impact on economic growth, with physical capital having the most significant effect - a 1% increase in capital leads to a 0.58% increase in economic growth, significant at the 5% level. These findings suggest that investments in physical capital, human capital, and attracting FDI, as well as promoting trade, are crucial for sustainable economic growth in the long run (Siddique et al., 2017). The GDP have positive impact on economic growth. previous study concluded that the study reveals a long-run co-integrated relationship between foreign direct investment, employed labor force, and gross domestic product (GDP) in Pakistan, indicating that real output growth (GDP) has a long-term relationship with savings, foreign direct investment, and employed labor force. However, the findings are inconclusive, as the F-statistic value falls between the lower and upper bound critical values, making it difficult to reject the null hypothesis of no co-integration among these variables. In other words, while there appears to be a long-run relationship between these variables, the results are not strong enough to conclusively confirm co-integration. Further analysis and testing may be necessary to determine the nature of this relationship and its significance for economic growth in Pakistan (kholua et al., 2022). Trade suggest that increasing international trade can improve economic growth by providing access to new markets, resources and technologies, previous study concluded that the analysis reveals that total trade and labor force have a significant relationship with economic growth, while total debt and education have an insignificant relationship. The high R-Bar Squared value of 0.98 indicates a strong correlation among the variables. Additionally, the F-statistic is significant at the 1% level, indicating an excellent overall fit of the model. The test for long-run relationships among the variables in equation (1) yields significant results. Following Bahmani-Oskooee and Bohal (2000), we acknowledge that the results of this first step are sensitive to the chosen lag length in equation (2). Given our use of annual data, we opted for a shorter lag length to ensure robust findings (Butt et al., 2008). The significant of labor and capital suggest that investing in human capital and physical infrastructure is crucial for economic growth. according to previous study the analysis reveals that gross fixed capital formation (private sector) has a significantly positive impact on economic growth in the long run, consistent with Lach (2010). However, it has a significantly negative effect in the short run. This suggests that while gross fixed capital formation is crucial for long-term economic growth, its short-term impact may be limited. Gross fixed capital formation encompasses various capital goods, including equipment, machinery, furniture, structures, land improvements, and cultivated assets in orchard development and livestock sectors. As Pakistan is a developing economy with limited resources, it may not be able to invest in these sectors simultaneously, leading to reduced productivity and negative economic growth in the short run. Nevertheless, investment in these sectors contributes to long-term economic development, as noted by Arby & Batool (2007). Table 8 shows the ARDL long-run estimates.

Table 8: ARDL Long-Run Estimates

Levels Equation				
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INTERNET	1875070	65044.06	28.82768	0.0000
FDI	0.002073	0.000848	2.444996	0.0501
EC	-3356313	704401.5	-4.764772	0.0031
CAPITAL	781428.9	261036.1	2.993566	0.0242

Levels Equation				
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TRADE	662322.3	246108.9	2.691175	0.0360
C	48082606	8424830	5.707249	0.0013

Source: Author's estimation.

The results suggest that internet penetration, economic cooperation, capital, and trade have significant long-run relationships with the dependent variable, while foreign direct investment has a marginally significant relationship. The coefficients and p-values provide further insight into the strength and significance of these relationships. This study reveals a long-run co-integrated relationship between economic growth and its determinants, including foreign direct investment, savings, and employed labor force. Previous findings indicate a positive and significant relationship between all explanatory variables and real GDP growth in Pakistan. Specifically, the results show that: A 1% increase in savings leads to a 3.3001% increase in economic growth. A 1% increase in foreign direct investment (FDI) leads to a 0.6194% increase in output GDP. A 1% increase in employed labor force leads to a 0.4155% increase in real GDP growth. These findings are consistent with previous studies (Rahman & Bakar, 2019; Wang & Choi, 2021; Malik, 2015; Rahman et al., 2019; Hamid & Pichler, 2009) and contradict the findings of earlier literature (Mahmood & Siddiqui, 2000; Alam et al., 2017). In long-run GDP has significance impact on labor force as previous study reveals that Labor Force has a significant long-term relationship with GDP, indicating that changes in the labor force have a lasting impact on economic growth. In contrast, External Debt has an insignificant negative association with economic growth, suggesting that debt levels do not significantly hinder economic growth. Additionally, Total Trade and Education are found to have no significant impact on economic growth. (Butt et al. 2008). The analysis reveals that labor force participation has a positive and significant impact on economic growth in both the long and short run, similar to Trade. This highlights the crucial role the labor force plays in Pakistan's economic development. This finding is consistent with previous research by Asghar, Awan, & Rehman (2012), which also emphasized the importance of labor force participation in driving economic growth. The results suggest that policies aimed at increasing labor force participation, such as education and training programs, can have a positive impact on Pakistan's economic growth and development. According to my finding's gross fixed capital has a significant impact on labor force but previous study concluded that A one-unit increase in Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) leads to a 0.24-unit increase in Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC). A one-unit increase in Labor Force Participation Rate (LFPR) results in a 0.011-unit increase in GDPPC. Inflation has a negative relationship with GDPPC A one-unit increase in Life Expectancy leads to a 0.25-unit increase in GDPPC, and this relationship is statistically significant. Additionally, the results show that Gross Fixed Capital Formation, are statistically significant explanatory variables, while the other variables are insignificant (Awan et al., 2017). The study highlights the importance of savings, FDI, and employed labor force in driving economic growth in Pakistan, providing valuable insights for policymakers to design effective strategies for sustainable economic development. Table 9 shows the ARDL bounds estimates.

Table 9: ARDL Bounds Estimates

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signify	I (0)	I (1)
		Asymptotic: n=1000		
F-statistic	10.49473	10%	2.08	3
k	5	5%	2.39	3.38
		2.5%	2.7	3.73
		1%	3.06	4.15

Source: Author's estimation.

Based on the output, it appears that the test statistic value (10.49473) is greater than the critical values for all significance levels, indicating that there is a long-run relationship (cointegration) between the variables. However, it's important to note that the sample size is relatively small (23), and the finite sample critical values may be more appropriate for this analysis. This test shows that variables have long-run relationship exists and have cointegration.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study examines the determinants of labor market participation in Pakistan, aiming to uncover the factors that influence individuals' decisions to join the workforce. By analyzing data from 1998 to 2022, the study uses the ARDL model to estimate the short-run and long-run relationships between variables. The results of the ARDL bounds test show the existence of co-integration between economic growth, trade, FDI, capital, and internet usage. The short-run results of the ARDL are significant and positive, and the error correction term is significant, indicating that variables tend to return to their long-run equilibrium over time. The short-term dynamics of the variables are captured by the first differences. In the long run, the internet has the strongest significant positive coefficient, indicating a strong long-run relationship with the dependent variable, while other variables also have significant long-run relationships with the dependent variable. The study shows that an increase in labor positively impacts FDI, capital, the internet, economic growth, and trade. Results also show unidirectional causality from economic growth to labor and from capital to labor, with

no causality between trade and labor, but bidirectional causality between FDI and internet, and between capital and FDI.

To address these findings, the government should focus on improving education in the country, including training programs and quality educational institutions to enhance human skills. Countries with policies that attract more FDI have the potential to increase their economic growth. This research provides valuable insights for policymakers seeking to understand labor market dynamics in Pakistan and develop strategies to boost labor force participation, ultimately promoting economic growth and development.

Policy Recommendations:

Short-term (0-2 years):

- Launch a nationwide digital literacy campaign to equip the workforce with basic digital skills, partnering with the private sector to provide training and resources.
- Develop a national online job platform to connect workers with employment opportunities, collaborating with private companies to list job openings and provide training resources.
- Implement targeted incentives to attract FDI in labor sectors, streamlining regulations and procedures to facilitate foreign investment.
- Introduce trade facilitation measures to reduce export costs and increase efficiency, and enhance regional trade agreements to access neighboring markets.

These short-term recommendations aim to address immediate labor market challenges, enhance digital literacy, and attract foreign investment to stimulate economic growth.

Medium-term (2-5 years):

- Develop and implement comprehensive education and skills development programs aligned with labor market demands, enhancing technical education to develop job-relevant skills.
- Invest in infrastructure development, including transportation, energy, and communication networks, to enhance connectivity and access to markets.
- Encourage private sector investment in labor-intensive industries, diversify trade partners and products to reduce dependence on a few markets, and negotiate free trade agreements with key trading partners.
- Promote innovation and entrepreneurship through funding and support programs, and develop business incubators and accelerators to support start-ups and SME growth.

These medium-term policies aim to address structural challenges, enhance education and skills, and promote industrial growth, innovation, and entrepreneurship to drive sustainable economic growth and job creation.

Long-term (5-10 years):

- Invest in early childhood education and training programs, and develop and implement a comprehensive national skills development strategy.
- Establish research and development institutions and innovation hubs, encouraging private sector investment in R&D and innovation.
- Develop and implement a comprehensive national infrastructure development plan, investing in transportation, energy, and communication networks.
- Work on developing and implementing a comprehensive industrial transformation strategy, negotiating and implementing comprehensive free trade agreements with key trading partners.
- Develop a social protection strategy to ensure universal access to healthcare, education, and social security.

These long-term policies aim to address deep-seated structural challenges, develop human capital, drive innovation and industrial transformation, and promote sustainable economic growth and development. They require a long-term commitment and a stable policy environment to bear fruit.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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